

Do imbalance situation stimulate a spinal straightening reflex in patient with adolescent idiopathic scoliosis?

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BACKGROUND: Correlation between balance and Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis (AIS) is still unclear. To identify the most useful type of physical exercises to be proposed for conservative treatment, is interesting to explore better this field.

AIM: Evaluation of change of scoliosis curves in a group AIS patients while submitted to an unbalancing situation

DESIGN: pre-post trial

POPULATION: 14 AIS patients (46 curves), 12 to 15 years old, with $19.3 \pm 9.9^\circ$ Cobb curves.

METHODS: Assessment has been made using GOALS (Global Optoelectronic Approach for Locomotion and Spine), a non-ionising instrument that allow a 3D reconstruction of the spine. We evaluated the patients twice in a standardised standing position: on the floor, and on a sway bench. For statistics we used paired T test; to consider significant a variation, due to the high precision of the instrument, we considered 1° Cobb.

RESULTS: on the sway bench there was a statistically (but not clinically) significant reduction of the curves from $19.3 \pm 9.9^\circ$ to $18.6 \pm 9.6^\circ$. This was confirmed considering the average of the curves of each patient, but not when considering the worst curve (from $26.1 \pm 9.4^\circ$ to $25.4 \pm 10.2^\circ$), where statistical significance was not reached presumably because of the reduced sample. Looking at the curves, 13% worsened and 33% improved, versus 14% and 43% respectively looking at the patients.

CONCLUSION: We did not find similar reactions in all patients, even if in general a spinal straightening reflex while on a sway bench appears. In any case these variations are of low degree.